

DR Congo's National Energy Compacts (M300) plan for 2030

Benjamin HODIA KIBUNGU, Ministry of Water Resources and Electricity, DRC
(benjikibungu1@gmail.com)

May 2025

- - Keywords

M300, National Energy Compacts, DRC, OnSSET, Electrification

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the entire trainers' team of OnSSET Track – Energy Modelling Platform for Africa 2025, especially **Andreas Sahlberg**, **Julian Cantor** and **Thierry Odou** for their support in mastering this energy modelling tool.

This report is the outcome of a three-week training at the Energy Modelling Platform for Africa 2025, organized and provided by United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, Climate Compatible Growth, Sustainable Energy for All, International Renewable Energy Association, World Bank Group/ESMAP, Politecnico di Milano and World Resources Institute.

Participation in the event was supported by Sustainable Energy for All through funding from The Rockefeller Foundation. SEforALL acknowledges also its institutional funders Austrian Development Cooperation, Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Iceland, People's Postcode Lottery and Global Energy Alliance for People and Planet.

Finally, this material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) program. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) aims to raise electricity access from 21% to 62% by 2030 under the Mission 300 initiative, this implies connecting around 77 million people. Using the **OnSSET (Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool)**, a geospatial least-cost electrification modelling, two scenarios were analyzed: the Least Cost of Electricity (LCOE) scenario, favoring solar PV and mini-grids for cost-effective household electrification with private sector appeal, and the Largest Clusters scenario (LCS), which prioritizes large load centers with grid extensions. Despite a \$2.1 billion higher investment compared to LCOE scenario, LCS could be the way Government should go because it ensures market profitability and planned High Voltage lines viability, as well as the means to promote clean cooking, reducing pressure on the forest.

I would recommend considering for the future work to include prioritizing the Largest Clusters approach to aligning with productive demand and economic realities. This approach will enhance financial viability of planned grid extension and inclusiveness, supporting DRC's goal to expand electricity access and contribute to the broader Mission 300 objective of connecting 300 million Africans by 2030.

Some areas of improvement in the model could include optimizing HV lines routing to reduce costs and incorporating medium hydro plants (10-50 MW) to complement hybrid PV mini grids, as well as integrating productive uses, especially mining, into planning models is essential for sustainable energy market development in the case of DRC.

The report also identifies critical challenges such as financing gaps, infrastructure optimization, and the need to integrate productive demand, especially from mining activities, into planning models. These insights provide a roadmap for policymakers and stakeholders to accelerate equitable and sustainable energy access, fostering economic transformation and social inclusion across the DRC by 2030.

2. Methodology

The study employs the **OnSSET (Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool)**, a geospatial least-cost electrification model. OnSSET enables the analysis of optimal technology mixes and infrastructure expansion strategies to achieve national electrification targets under different scenarios using the LCOE as a metric to choose between alternatives.

The data sources for this study includes the National Electrification Master Plan (providing), and other sources as determined following (Table 1).

Table 1 : Data source Collection

Data	Sources
Planned high-voltage lines and capacity expansion targets	(MRHE, 2025)
Demographic data (covering population distribution, urban/rural split, and settlement sizes)	(WBG, 2023) (ENERGYDATA.INFO, 2025)
Electricity demand Tiers.	Based on the World Bank Multi-Tier Framework for urban, large rural, and small rural clusters
Cost and technical parameters (such as technology costs, investment requirements, and operational data for grid, mini-grid, and off-grid solutions) based on default parameters in the tool	Default parameters in OnSSET
Resources (solar, Wind, Hydro, grids, substations, etc.)	(Atlas, 2025) (Atlas, 2025) (ResourceMatters, s.d.).

The key assumptions of the study are: a timeframe from 2024 to 2030, a national electricity access target of 62% by 2030, the construction of 3,880 km of high-voltage lines as per national plans, the use of demand tiers (Urban: Tier 4, Large Rural: Tier 2, Small Rural: Tier 1), and prioritization of settlements for electrification based either on the lowest investment cost per capita or the largest settlement clusters.

Two main scenarios were modelled: the LCOE scenario, which prioritizes least-cost electrification per capita, and the Largest Clusters scenario (LCS), which prioritizes electrification of the largest settlements. The sensitivity of these scenarios resides on variations of the demand tiers for settlements (Urban, large rural and small rural), Routing of planned HV lines, and the priority to select which settlement to electrify first.

3. Results

In this EMP-A 2025, study for the DR Congo National Energy Compacts (M300) plan assesses how to raise electricity access from 21% to 62% by 2030 using OnSSET modelling tool.

In the LCOE scenario, 29% of new electrification is achieved via grid densification and extension mainly from planned HV lines. While a significant share (especially in rural areas) is provided with decentralized solutions such as solar PV and hybrid mini-grids (Figure 2). Under LCOE scenario, 33% of electrification is delivered by the planned HV grid, focusing on the largest settlements.

Figure 2: Electrified population by technology and technology mapping per scenario

The results show that to achieve a 62% (MRHE, 2025) electricity access rate by 2030, the DRC must install an additional capacity of 1761 MW under the LCOE scenario emphasizing more decentralized solutions like solar PV and mini-grids, while under the LCS scenario the analysis is suggesting around 2593 MW and relies more heavily On-grid based capacity to electrify larger settlements and ensure the profitability of planned HV lines (figure 3). LCS tends to increase substantially the mini-grids compared to LCOE scenario as for high load centers far from the grid, mini-grids appear the preferred least-cost technology.

Figure 3: New installed capacity per scenario

Regarding investment needs, both scenarios require substantial investments, with the majority allocated to grid extension and mini-grid deployment. The estimated investment in the Largest Clusters scenario is about \$2.1 billion than LCOE, reflecting the higher costs of extending the grid to large population centers but sometimes more remote, the average distance of clusters from the grid is 106 m (figure 4). Overall scenario costs range from \$7.4 to \$9.5 billion, with annual investment needs ranging from \$1.5 to \$1.9 billion.

Figure 4 : Investment costs per scenario

5. Discussion

According to the technology mix results, the LCOE scenario promotes more decentralized solutions such as solar PV and hybrid mini grids. These decentralized technologies are attractive for private sector investment and can be rapidly deployed. In addition, government needs to create a favorable business climate through more

attractive policies and develop regulatory instruments to protect investments and consumers.

On the other hand, LCS approach maximizes the profitability and utilization of planned transmission infrastructure, better supporting the economic case for large-scale grid investments. This explains why grid shares get a boost compared to LCOE Scenario although at a higher cost of \$2.1 billion.

In addition, according to the market viability and inclusiveness, the LCOE scenario is optimal for household electrification, especially in sparsely populated rural areas, due to its cost-efficiency and reliance on private-sector-friendly technologies. However, it may not ensure the full utilization or profitability of planned HV lines. The Largest Clusters scenario, while more costly and requiring greater government involvement, is more realistic for supporting productive uses (such as mining and industry) and ensuring the financial sustainability of grid infrastructure. It targets larger urban and rural agglomerations, where electricity demand and ability to pay are higher.

Finally, overall scenario costs (\$7.4 to \$9.5 Billion) represent up to 26% of the total budget needed in DRC's Mission 300 target. The difference between both scenarios is that the LCOE Scenario prioritizes the lowest investment cost per capita, relying more on decentralized, private-sector-driven solutions with lower total investment but less support for grid profitability and productive use integration. In contrast, the LCS focuses on electrifying the largest settlements through a higher share of grid-based electrification, maximizing high-voltage line utilization, which involves higher investment costs but better supports economic development and productive demand.

To achieve both inclusiveness and sustainability for DRC's electrification ambitions under Mission 300, I would recommend for future research prioritizing the Largest Clusters approach, optimizing HV line routing, integrating productive demand (especially mining), and complementing mini grids with medium hydro plants.

Also, future modelling should further refine productive use integration and high demand Tiers for settlements, considering clean cooking to reduce the use of wood energy and consequently the pressure on the forest.

7. Conclusion and recommendations

Participating in the OnSSET Track at the Energy Modelling Platform for Africa (EMP-A) 2025 offered profound knowledge in geospatial energy modeling and electrification planning. It has significantly improved skills in integrating spatial data and renewable resources to develop comprehensive energy strategies for countries. This training highlighted the essential role of comprehensive, data-driven methods for optimizing energy investments and advancing Africa's sustainable development, especially amid growing energy needs and climate challenges.

One of the main takeaways was recognizing the value of open-source tools like OnSSET in crafting tailored electrification solutions that effectively balance cost, accessibility, and environmental impact and allows anyone to keep track of the content. Drawing from this experience, I suggest enhancing the capacity of institutions across Africa to adopt and adapt these modelling tools, while encouraging stronger partnerships among governments, academic institutions, and the private sector.

Furthermore, ongoing knowledge sharing through initiatives like EMP-A will help speed up Africa's energy transformation and enhance planning capacity. Finally, embedding geospatial analysis into national energy frameworks will allow for more strategic investment decisions, ensuring fair and sustainable energy access in line with Africa's Agenda 2063, the Paris Agreement and moreover the M300 imitative goal

References

- Atlas, G. S., 2025. *Global Solar Atlas*. [Online]
Available at: <https://globalsolaratlas.info/map>
[Accessed may 2025].
- Atlas, G. W., 2025. *Global Wind Atlas*. [Online]
Available at: <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/>
- ENERGYDATA.INFO, 2025. [Online]
Available at: <https://energydata.info/>
- MRHE, 2025. *Terms of reference for the development of a National Master Plan for Low-Cost Electrification in the Democratic Republic of Congo*. s.l.:Ministry of Water Resources and Electricity, DRC.
- ResourceMatters, n.d. *Congo epela*. [Online]
Available at: <https://congoepela.resourcematters.org/fr#loc=4.69/-4.83/25.66>
[Accessed 6 may 2025].
- WBG, 2023. *World Bank Group*. [Online]
Available at: <https://donnees.banquemondiale.org/indicateur/SP.POP.TOTL?locations=CD>

EMP-A

